

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART XIII

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The synthesis of 2-hydroxy-4-methylquinoline-6-arsonic acid is described.

Organic arsenicals have proved valuable in the treatment of syphilis, trypanosomiasis and amoebiasis. Some also have been found to possess antimalarial properties: In a previous communication it has been pointed out that compounds containing both the quinoline nucleus and arsenic in their molecule would seem to offer good possibilities of having therapeutic value in chronic malaria.

The classical method of Knorr (*Annalen*, 1886, 236, 75) and that of Conrad and Limpach (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 944) have now been applied for the synthesis of some new quinoline-arsonic acid derivatives.

When *para*-arsanilic acid is allowed to react with ethyl acetoacetate at 160-165°, a mixture of *p*-acetoacetylaminophenylarsonic acid (I) and ethyl β -[phenyl-(4-arsonic acid) amino] crotonate (II) is obtained.

The compound (I), which contains a ketonic group, reacts with phenylhydrazine to yield the phenylhydrazine salt of the corresponding phenylhydrazone.

It is interesting to note that the sodium salt of the compound (I) is structurally related to Tryparsamide (III) and Neocryl (IV).

Some claims have been made that Neocryl is less toxic to the optic nerve than Tryparsamide and possibly more effective in neurosyphilis (*cf.* Murgatroyd, *Ann. Trop. Med.*, 1937, 31, 472; Lum, *Chem. Products*, 1939, 2, 99; Acres, *Trans. Roy. Soc. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1940, 34, 281). Both (III) and (IV) are derivatives of *para*-arsanilic acid and both contain the -CO.NH- group. The question naturally arises as to whether the grouping, -CO.NH-, has any special significance in connection with the activity of these drugs, since some amide-substituted phenylarsine oxides also have been recently found to show high chemotherapeutic index in the treatment of rabbit syphilis (*cf.* Eagle, Hogan, Doak and Steinman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1236). It will therefore be worth while to see if the compound (I) has any effect on trypanosomiasis and also on neurosyphilis.

When the compound (I) is treated with concentrated sulphuric acid at 60°, the quinoline-arsonic acid derivative (VI) is obtained (*cf.* Knorr, *loc. cit.*). Whereas the compound (I) gives a deep red colouration with ferric chloride and a phenylhydrazone (V), the com-

pound (VI) does neither give any distinctive colouration with ferric chloride nor any phenylhydrazone.

The cyclisation of the compound (II), which does not melt even at 300° , with concentrated sulphuric acid at room temperature was attempted but the product isolated could not be purified, due to its insolubility in organic solvents and also in hot water.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Condensation of Ethyl Acetoacetate with p-Arsanilic Acid : Formation of p-Acetoacetylaminophenylarsonic Acid (I) and Ethyl β -[Phenyl-(4-arsonic acid) amino] crotonate (II).—*p*-Arsanilic acid (100 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (30 g.) were thoroughly mixed together and heated in an oil-bath at 160 - 165° for 20 hours. The residual liquid was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the solid left was cooled, thoroughly triturated with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid to remove the unreacted *p*-arsanilic acid, filtered and thoroughly washed with water. The mass was next purified by solution in aqueous sodium carbonate and reprecipitation with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained was dried and extracted twice with boiling alcohol and filtered. A portion went into solution, leaving some quantity which was found insoluble in boiling alcohol.

The alcoholic solution, on evaporation, left a residue (compound I) which was twice crystallised from 50% alcohol (charcoal) in brown crystalline powder (10 g.) which does not melt even at 300° . (Found : N, 4.34 ; As, 24.68. $C_{10}H_{12}O_5NAs$ requires N, 4.65 ; As, 24.91 per cent). An alcoholic solution of this compound (I) gives a deep red colouration with ferric chloride.

The portion (compound II), found insoluble in boiling alcohol, was washed several times with hot alcohol. It was found insoluble in boiling water and in ordinary organic solvents, and was purified by solution in aqueous sodium carbonate and precipitation with dilute hydrochloric acid. On drying the compound (II) was obtained as a brown crystalline powder (yield 5 g.), which does not melt even at 300° . (Found : N, 4.17 ; As, 23.20. $C_{12}H_{16}O_5NAs$ require N, 4.25 ; As, 22.76 per cent).

p-(Acetophenylhydrazone-acetylamino)-phenylarsonic Acid (V).—To a hot alcoholic solution of the compound (I ; 10 g.) phenylhydrazine (10 g.) was added, and the solution was then heated under reflux on the wire-gauze for about 2 hours, when a brown crystalline solid was precipitated. It was filtered and washed thoroughly with hot alcohol and then with ether. It is sparingly soluble in hot alcohol and practically insoluble in hot water. It was crystallised from large quantity of alcohol in brownish rectangular plates, which do not melt even at 300° . It is insoluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate and is the phenylhydrazine salt of compound (V). [Found : N, 15.93. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4N_2As$ ($2PhNH-NH_2$) requires N, 16.14 per cent].

The above salt is, however, soluble in cold dilute caustic soda solution and the alkaline solution, on acidification with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold, precipitated a brownish solid (compound V ; yield 5 g.) which does not melt even at 300° . (Found : N, 10.58 ; As, 18.72. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4N_2As$ requires N, 10.74 ; As, 19.18 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-4-methylquinoline-6-arsonic Acid (VI).—Concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) was slowly added to the above compound (I; 5 g.), when gradually, on shaking, a thick clear solution was obtained with slight rise in temperature. The solution was then heated in an oil-bath at 60° for 3 hours and then allowed to stand overnight. Next day the solution was poured into ice-water under stirring, when a dark solid was precipitated. This substance is soluble in hot alcohol but it did not show any tendency to crystallise from alcohol. It was, however, purified twice by adding excess of ether to an alcoholic solution of the substance, when an amorphous mass was precipitated, which on standing for about 30 minutes turned into a chocolate-coloured crystalline powder (yield 2 g.), which does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 5.28; As, 26.02. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4NAs$ requires N, 4.94; As, 26.50 per cent). With ferric chloride an alcoholic solution of this substance does not give any distinctive colouration but gives a brown precipitate. It does not form any phenylhydrazone.

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BISMUTH IODIDE COMPLEXES OF SOME 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

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For pharmacological study against amoebiasis, bismuth iodide complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline, 5-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline, 5:7-dichloro-8-hydroxyquinoline, 7-iodo-5-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline and 5:7-di-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline have been prepared.

In recent years compounds like 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (Vioform) and 5:7-di-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (Diodoquin) have proved extremely useful in the treatment of chronic and relapsing cases of amoebic dysentery. Emetine bismuth iodide and Kurchi bismuth iodide have also been found to be useful in the treatment of chronic amoebic dysentery. However, as a result of extensive clinical trials of these and other important chemotherapeutic drugs on cases of amoebic dysentery in the army in India, Leishman and Kelsall (*Lancet*, 1944, p. 231) have found that there are some relapsing cases which resist the action of all these drugs or a combination of some of them. They have felt the urgent need for the discovery of a new, more potent amoebicidal drug which will effect cure in chronic and relapsing cases.

In the search for an ideal amoebicidal drug, bismuth iodide complexes of some halogen derivatives of 8-hydroxyquinoline have now been prepared and characterised. They have been prepared by the interaction of a cold, freshly prepared Dragendorff's reagent with the hydrochloric acid solution of requisite quantity of the respective halogen derivative of 8-hydroxyquinoline. All these complex salts are of deep orange colour, soluble in acetone and have definite melting points.

The analyses of the component parts of these complexes have been carried out according to the process adopted in the standardisation of Kurchi bismuth iodide (Mukherjee, *J. & Proc. Inst. of Chem., India*, 1944, 16, 64), slightly modified. In the estimation